

Proof of the binary Goldbach conjecture

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Abstract.

In this paper, a "local" algorithm is determined for the construction of two recurrent sequences of positive primes (U_{2n}) and (V_{2n}), (U_{2n}) dependent of (V_{2n}), such that for each integer $n \geq 2$, their sum is equal to $2n$. To form this, a third sequence of primes (W_{2n}) is defined for any integer $n \geq 3$ by : $W_{2n} = \text{Sup}(p \in \mathcal{P} : p \leq 2n - 3)$, where \mathcal{P} is the infinite set of primes. The Goldbach conjecture has been proved for all even integers $2n$ between 4 and $4 \cdot 10^{18}$. In the table of terms of Goldbach sequences given in appendix 10, values of the order of $2n = 10^{1000}$ are reached. This "finite ascent and descent" method proves the binary Goldbach conjecture ; an analogous proof by recurrence is established and an increase in U_{2n} by $0.7(\ln(2n))^{2.2}$ is justified. Moreover, the Lagrange-Lemoine-Levy conjecture and its generalization, the Bezout-Goldbach conjecture, are proven by the same type of procedure.

Key words.

Prime numbers, Prime Number Theorem, binary Goldbach conjecture, Lagrange-Lemoine-Levy conjecture, Bezout-Goldbach conjecture, gaps between consecutive primes, .

1 Overview

Number theory, " the queen of mathematics " studies the structures and properties defined on integers and primes (see Euclid [11], Hadamard [13], Hardy, Wright [14], Landau [20], Tchebychev [32]).

Numerous problems have been raised and conjectures made, the statements of which are often simple but very difficult to prove. These main components include :

Elementary arithmetic :

* Determination and properties of primes, operations on integers (basic operations, congruence, gcd, lcm,).

* Decomposition of integers into products or sums of primes (fundamental theorem of arithmetic, decomposition of large numbers, cryptography, and Goldbach's conjecture).

Analytical number theory :

- * Distribution of primes (Prime Number Theorem, Hadamard [13], De la Vallée-Poussin [33], Littlewood [23] and Erdos [10], The Riemann hypothesis).
- * Gaps between consecutive primes, Bombieri, Davenport, [3], Cramer [8], Baker, Harman, Iwaniec, Pintz [4], [5],[18], Granville [12], Shanks [27], Tchebychev [32] and Zhang [36].

Algebraic, probabilistic, combinatorial and algorithmic number theories.

- * Modular arithmetic, diophantine approximations, equations, arithmetic functions and algebraic geometry.

2 Definitions, notations and background

(2.1) The integers n, k, p, q, r, \dots used in this article are always positive.

(2.2) Let \mathcal{P} the infinite set of positive primes p_k (called simply primes) :

$$(p_1 = 2 ; p_2 = 3 ; p_3 = 5 ; p_4 = 7 ; p_5 = 11 ; p_6 = 13 ; \dots).$$

(2.3) The writing of large numbers (see appendix 10) is simplified using the following constants

$$M = 10^9 ; R = 4.10^8 ; G = 10^{100} ; S = 10^{500} ; T = 10^{1000}$$

(2.4) $\ln(x)$ denotes the neperian logarithm of the strictly positive real x , ($x > 0$).

(2.5) Let (W_{2n}) be the sequence of primes defined by :

$$(2.5.1) \quad \text{For any integer } n \geq 3, \quad W_{2n} = \text{Sup}(p \in \mathcal{P} : p \leq 2n - 3)$$

(2.6) Any sequence denoted by $(G_{2n}) = (U_{2n}; V_{2n})$ verifying (2.6.1) is called a **Goldbach sequence** :

(2.6.1) (For any integer $n \geq 2$ U_{2n} and V_{2n} are primes and $U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n$).

(2.7) Iwaniec, Pintz [18] have shown that for a sufficiently large integer n there is always a prime between $n - n^{23/42}$ and n . Baker, Harman [4], [5] concluded that, there is a prime in the interval $[n; n + o(n^{0.525})]$. Thus this results provides an increase of the gap between two consecutive primes p_k and p_{k+1} of the form :

$$(2.7.1) \quad \forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists k_\varepsilon \in \mathbb{N}^* \text{ such that : } \forall k \in \mathbb{N}^* \text{ with } k > k_\varepsilon \quad p_{k+1} - p_k < \varepsilon p_k^{0.525}$$

(2.8) According to the Cramer-Maier-Nicely conjecture [1], [3], [8], [12], [24], [25], for any real $c > 2$, for any integer $k \geq 500$,

$$(2.8.1) \quad p_{k+1} - p_k \leq 0.7(\ln(p_k))^c \quad \text{(with probability one)}.$$

3 Introduction

Chen [6], Hardy, Littlewood [15], Hegfoltt, Platt [16], Ramaré, Saouter [26], Tao [31], Tchebychev [32] and Vinogradov [34] have taken important steps and obtained promising results on the Goldbach conjecture. Indeed, Helfgott, Platt [16] proved the weak Goldbach conjecture in 2013.

Silva, Herzog, Pardi [29] held the record for calculating the terms of Goldbach sequences after determining pairs of primes $(U_{2n}; V_{2n})$ verifying :

$$(3.1) \quad \text{For any integer } n, (4 \leq 2n \leq 4.10^{18}) : (U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n).$$

In previous research work, there is no explicit construction of recurrent sequences of Goldbach primes of the form : $(G_{2n}) = (U_{2n}; V_{2n})$ satisfying for any integer $n \geq 2$ the equality : $(U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n)$.

In this article, two sequences of primes are developed using a simple and efficient algorithm to compute for any integer $n \geq 3$ by successive iterations any term U_{2n} and V_{2n} of a Goldbach sequence. Using Maxima scientific software on a personal computer, Silva's record is broken, and the values $2n = 10^{500}$ and even $2n = 10^{1000}$ are reached. The proof of the binary Goldbach conjecture can be established on the same principle, using reasoning by recurrence. Moreover, the Lagrange-Lemoine-Lévy conjectures [9], [17], [19], [24], [25], [30], [35] and its generalization, the Bezout-Goldbach conjecture are validated.

Using case disjunction reasoning, we construct two recurrent sequences of primes (V_{2n}) and (U_{2n}) according to the sequence (W_{2n}) by the following process. For any integer $n \geq 2$,

$$(3.2) \quad (U_4 = 2 ; V_4 = 2)$$

Let n be an integer : $(n \geq 3)$.

1) **Either**,

$(2n - W_{2n})$ is a prime, then V_{2n} and U_{2n} are defined directly in terms of W_{2n} .

2) **Either**,

$(2n - W_{2n})$ is a composite number, then V_{2n} and U_{2n} are defined from the preceding terms of the sequence (G_{2n}) .

4 Principle of proof

To determine pairs of primes that verify the Goldbach conjecture, three sequences of primes (W_{2n}) , (V_{2n}) , (U_{2n}) are defined and verify the following properties :

$$(4.1) \quad \lim V_{2n} = +\infty .$$

(4.2) For any integer $n \geq 2$, V_{2n} is defined as a function of $W_{2n} = \text{Sup}(p \in \mathcal{P} : p \leq 2n - 3)$.

(4.3) (W_{2n}) is an increasing sequence that contains all primes except the prime $p_1 = 2$.

$$(4.4) \quad \lim W_{2n} = +\infty$$

(4.5) (U_{2n}) is a complementary sequence of negligible primes with respect to $(2n)$.

(4.6) For any integer $n \geq 3$,

If $(2n - W_{2n})$ is a prime " special case ",

then V_{2n} and U_{2n} are defined by :

$$(4.7) \quad V_{2n} = W_{2n} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n}$$

Otherwise, if $(2n - W_{2n})$ is a composite number "general case"

we search for two previous terms of the sequence (G_{2n}) , $(U_{2(n-k)})$ and $V_{2(n-k)}$ satisfying the following conditions :

$$(4.8) \quad U_{2(n-k)}, V_{2(n-k)} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{2(n-k)} + 2k \quad \text{are primes}$$

$$U_{2(n-k)} + V_{2(n-k)} = 2(n - k)$$

(which is always possible ; see the proof in Theorem 5).

Thus, by setting :

$$(4.9) \quad V_{2n} = V_{2(n-k)} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{2n} = U_{2(n-k)} + 2k$$

two new primes V_{2n} and U_{2n} satisfying (4.10) are generated.

$$(4.10) \quad U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n .$$

This process is then repeated, incrementing n by one unit : $(n \rightarrow n + 1)$.

5 Theorem

There exists a recursive Goldbach sequence of primes $(G_{2n}) = (U_{2n} ; V_{2n})$ satisfying for any integer $n \geq 2$:

$$U_{2n} \text{ and } V_{2n} \text{ are primes and their sum is equal to } 2n.$$

$$(5.1) \quad (U_{2n}, V_{2n} \in \mathcal{P} \text{ and } U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n)$$

(5.2) An algorithm can be used to explicitly compute any term U_{2n} and V_{2n} .

Proof of Theorem 5.

FIRST METHOD :

For any integer $n \geq 3$,

If $(2n - W_{2n})$ is a prime,

then V_{2n} and U_{2n} are defined by :

$$(5.3) \quad V_{2n} = W_{2n} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n}$$

Otherwise, if $(2n - W_{2n})$ is a composite number ,

we use the previous terms of the sequence (G_{2n}) .

For any integer q such that : $(1 \leq q \leq n - 3)$, we have : $3 \leq U_{2(n-q)} \leq n$.

For any integer k such that $(4 \leq 2k \leq n - 1)$, there are two primes p_m and p_r , $(m > r)$ in the interval $[4 ; n]$ such that :

$$(5.4) \quad p_m - p_r = 2k$$

(see Bombieri, Davenport [1], Cramer [8], Iwaniec, Pintz [18] , Tchebychev [32]).

Then there is an integer k verifying , $(4 \leq 2k \leq n - 3)$ such that :

$$(5.5) \quad R_{2n} = U_{2(n-k)} + 2k \quad \text{is a prime}$$

The smallest integer k denoted k_n such that R_{2n} is a prime is chosen. So let :

$$(5.6) \quad U_{2n} = U_{2(n-k_n)} + 2k_n \quad \text{and} \quad V_{2n} = V_{2(n-k_n)}$$

(These two terms are primes)

In the previous steps two primes $U_{2(n-k_n)}$ and $V_{2(n-k_n)}$ whose sum is equal to $2(n - k_n)$ were determined.

$$(5.7) \quad U_{2(n-k_n)} + V_{2(n-k_n)} = 2(n - k_n)$$

By adding the term k_n to each member of the equality (5.6), it follows :

$$(5.8) \quad U_{2(n-k_n)} + 2k_n + V_{2(n-k_n)} = 2(n - k_n) + 2k_n$$

$$(5.9) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad [U_{2(n-k_n)} + 2k_n] + V_{2(n-k_n)} = 2n$$

$$(5.10) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n$$

Finally, for any integer $n \geq 3$, this algorithm determines two sequences of primes (U_{2n}) and (V_{2n}) verifying Goldbach's conjecture.

SECOND METHOD :

The demonstration can be made using the following strong recurrence principle.

Let $P(n)$ be the following property defined for any integer $n \geq 2$ by :

$P(n)$: " For any integer p satisfying : ($2 \leq p \leq n$) , there exists two primes U_{2p} and V_{2p} such their sum is equal to $2p$: ($U_{2p} + V_{2p} = 2p$) " .

Let's show by strong recurrence that $P(n)$ is true for any integer $n \geq 2$.

a) $P(2)$ is true : it suffices to choose $U_4 = V_4 = 2$.

b) Let's show that the property $P(n)$ is hereditary : (i.e for any integer $n \geq 2$ $P(n) \Rightarrow P(n+1)$)

Assume property $P(n)$ is true,

If ($2(n+1) - W_{2(n+1)}$) is a prime.

then $V_{2(n+1)}$ and $U_{2(n+1)}$ are defined by :

$$(5.11) \quad V_{2(n+1)} = W_{2(n+1)} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{2(n+1)} = 2(n+1) - W_{2(n+1)}$$

Otherwise, if ($2(n+1) - W_{2(n+1)}$) is a composite number.

There exists an integer k to obtain two terms $U_{2(n+1-k)}$ and $V_{2(n+1-k)}$ satisfying the following conditions :

$$(5.12) \quad U_{2(n+1-k)}, V_{2(n+1-k)} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{2(n+1-k)} + 2k \quad \text{are primes}$$

$$U_{2(n+1-k)} + V_{2(n+1-k)} = 2(n+1-k)$$

(which is always possible : see first method).

Thus, by setting :

$$(5.13) \quad V_{2(n+1)} = V_{2(n+1-k)} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{2(n+1)} = U_{2(n+1-k)} + 2k$$

two new primes $V_{2(n+1)}$ and $U_{2(n+1)}$ satisfying ($U_{2(n+1)} + V_{2(n+1)} = 2(n+1)$) are generated.

It follows that $P(n+1)$ is true, then the property $P(n)$ is hereditary : ($P(n) \Rightarrow P(n+1)$).

Therefore, for any integer $n \geq 2$ the property $P(n)$ is true ; it follows that :

$\forall n \geq 2$ there are two primes U_{2n} and V_{2n} and such their sum is $2n$: ($U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n$)

6 Lemma

The sequence (U_{2n}) verifies the following increase : For any integer $n \geq 65$,

$$(6.1) \quad U_{2n} \leq (2n)^{0.55}$$

Proof of Lemma 6.

According to the programm 9.2 and appendix 10, the increase (6.1) is verified for any integer n such that : $(65 \leq n \leq 2000)$. For any integer $n > 2000$, the proof is established by recurrence. For this purpose, let $P1(n)$ be the following property :

(6.2) $P1(n)$: " There exists a strictly increasing sequence of positive numbers (C_n) such that :

$$U_{2n} \leq C_n (2n)^{0.525} "$$

a) $P1(2000)$ is true according to program 9.2 and the table in appendix 10.

b) For any integer $n \geq 2000$, let's show that $P1(n)$ is hereditary, (i.e $P1(n) \Rightarrow P1(n+1)$)

Assume that $P1(n)$ is true : then,

If $(2(n+1) - W_{2(n+1)})$ is a prime,

then $V_{2(n+1)}$ and $U_{2(n+1)}$ are defined by :

$$(6.2) \quad V_{2(n+1)} = W_{2(n+1)} \text{ and } U_{2(n+1)} = 2(n+1) - W_{2(n+1)}$$

According to the results in [4], [5], [18], there is a constant $K > 0$ such that :

$$(n+1) - K(2(n+1))^{0.525} < W_{2(n+1)} < 2(n+1)$$

$$\Rightarrow U_{2(n+1)} < K(2(n+1))^{0.525}$$

$$\Rightarrow U_{2(n+1)} \leq C_{n+1} (2(n+1))^{0.525}$$

Otherwise, if $(2(n+1) - W_{2(n+1)})$ is a composite number,

$$(6.4) \quad \exists p \in \mathbb{N}^* / \quad U_{2(n+1)} = U_{2(n+1-p)} + 2p$$

According to [4], [5], [18], the smallest integer p defined in (6.4) verifies:

$$(6.5) \quad 2p < K (U_{2(n+1-p)})^{0.525} \text{ and } U_{2(n+1-p)} < C_{n+1-p} (2(n+1-p))^{0.525}$$

It follows : $U_{2(n+1)} < K C_{n+1-p}^{0.525} (2(n+1-p))^{0.275625} + C_{n+1-p} (2(n+1-p))^{0.525}$

Then

$$(6.6) \quad U_{2(n+1)} < C_{n+1} (2(n+1))^{0.525}$$

and, by setting : $C_n = (2n)^{0.025}$ it follows :

$$(6.7) \quad U_{2(n+1)} < (2(n+1))^{0.55}$$

$P1(n+1)$ is true then $P1(n)$ is hereditary. So for any integer $n \geq 2000$, the property $P1(n)$ is true.

(The inequality (6.7) is verified with the aid of the software Maple studying the functions of the type $f : x \rightarrow ax^{0.275625} + bx^{0.525}$ increased by $g : x \rightarrow x^{0.55}$ with $a, b > 0$).

* **Remark.** A more precise estimate can be obtained using the Cippola or Axler frames, [7], [2].

7 Theorem

For any integer $n \geq 3$, it is easy to check :

7.1 (W_{2n}) is a positive increasing sequence of primes.

7.2 $\{W_{2n} : n \in \mathbb{N}^*\} \cup \{2\} = \mathcal{P}$

7.3 $\lim W_{2n} = +\infty$

7.4 (V_{2n}) is a sequence of primes.

The following results are validated with **probability one** :

7.5 $n \leq V_{2n} \leq W_{2n}$

7.6 $3 \leq 2n - W_{2n} \leq U_{2n} \leq n$

7.7 $\lim V_{2n} = +\infty$

Proof of Theorem 7.

7.1 For any integer $n \geq 2$ let A_n be the following set : $A_n = \{p_k \in \mathcal{P} : p_k \leq 2n - 3\}$.

$A_n \subset A_{n+1}$ therefore, $W_{2n} \leq W_{2(n+1)}$, so the sequence (W_{2n}) is a positive increasing sequence of primes.

7.2 Any prime except $p_1 = 2$ is odd, hence the result.

7.3 $\lim W_{2n} = \lim p_n = +\infty$

7.4 By definition $V_{2n} = W_{2n}$ or there exists an integer $k \leq n - 2$ such that : $V_{2n} = V_{2(n-k)}$; so, by recurrence the terms of the sequence (V_{2n}) are primes ; moreover, there exists a strictly increasing sub-sequence (V'_{2n}) of (V_{2n}) verifying $\lim (V'_{2n}) = +\infty$

7.5 According to Lemma 6, for any integer $n \geq 65$, $U_{2n} < (2n)^{0.55}$; therefore $U_{2n} < (2n)^{0.55} < n$ and,

$$V_{2n} = 2n - U_{2n} > 2n - n > n.$$

For any integer $n / (3 \leq n \leq 65)$ verification is carried out according to the computer program in paragraph 9.2 and the table in appendix 10.

7.6 According to 7.5, $n \leq V_{2n} \Rightarrow U_{2n} = 2n - V_{2n} \leq 2n - n \leq n$; moreover,

$$V_{2n} \leq W_{2n} \Rightarrow 2n - W_{2n} \leq 2n - V_{2n} = U_{2n}$$

7.7 By 7.5, for any integer $n \geq 2$, $n \leq V_{2n}$;

so,

$$\lim (V_{2n}) = +\infty .$$

8 Remarks

8.1 There are infinitely many integers n such that : $U_{2n} = 3, 5, 7$ or 11 .

8.2 $V_{2n} \sim 2n$ for $(n \rightarrow +\infty)$.

8.3 For any sufficiently large integer n , $(n \geq 5000)$: $U_{2n} \ll V_{2n}$ and $\lim \left(\frac{U_{2n}}{V_{2n}} \right) = 0$.

8.4 The smallest integer n such that :

$$U_{2n} \neq 2n - W_{2n} \text{ is obtained for } n = 49 \text{ and } G_{98} = (79 ; 19).$$

(This type of terms increases in the Goldbach sequence (G_{2n}) as n increases, in the sense of the Schnirelmann density, and there are an infinite number of them; their proportion per interval can be computed using the results given in [28]).

8.5 If $q \geq 5$ is an odd integer, we could generalize this algorithm with sequences (W'_{2n}) defined by :

$$(8.6.1) \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ with } n \geq \frac{(q+3)}{2} \quad W'_{2n} = \text{Sup}(p \in \mathcal{P} : p \leq 2n - q)$$

Other sequences (G'_{2n}) of Goldbach independent of (G_{2n}) are thus generated.

8.6 The sequence (G_{2n}) is extremal in the sense that for any integer $n \geq 2$ V_{2n} and U_{2n} are the largest and smallest possible primes such that : $U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n$.

8.7 The Cramer-Maier-Nicely conjecture [8], [12], [17], [19], [21], [22], [24], [25], [30] is verified with probability one. It leads to the following increase : For any integer $p \geq 500$,

$$(8.7.1) \quad U_{2p} \leq 0.7(\ln(2p))^{(2.2 - \frac{1}{p})} \quad (\text{with probability one})$$

The proof is similar to that of Lemma 6 using the same type of reasoning by recurrence, validated by the study of functions of the type : $f : x \rightarrow a g(x) + b (\ln(\square(\square)))^c$ with $a, b > 0$ and $c > 2$, with $g : x \rightarrow 0.7(\ln(x))^{(c - \frac{1}{x})}$ and $h : x \rightarrow 0.7(\ln(x))^{(2.2 - \frac{1}{x})}$ using Maple software.

* A better estimate can be obtained via [24], [25], [27].

8.8 According to Bombieri [3] and using the same method as in the proof of Lemma 6, on average, we obtain the following estimate of U_{2n} :

$$(8.8.1) \quad \forall \varepsilon > 0, \quad U_{2n} = O((\ln(2n))^{1.3+\varepsilon}), \quad (\text{on average})$$

9 Algorithm

9.1 Algorithm written in natural language.

Inputs :

Input four integer variables : k, N, n, P .

Input : $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3, p_3 = 5, p_4 = 7, \dots, p_N$ the first N primes.

: $n = 3$.

: $P = M, R, G, S$ or T as indicated in paragraph 2.

Algorithm body :

A) Compute : $W_{2n} = \text{Sup}(p \in \mathcal{P} : p \leq 2n - 3)$

If $T_{2n} = (2n - W_{2n})$ is a **prime**,

Let :

$$(9.1.1) \quad U_{2n} = T_{2n} \quad \text{and} \quad V_{2n} = W_{2n}$$

otherwise ,

B) If T_{2n} is a **composite number**,

Let : $k = 1$.

B.1) While $U_{2(n-k)} + 2k$ is a **composite number**,
 assign to k the value : $k + 1, (k \rightarrow k + 1)$.
 return to **B1)**

End while .

Assign to k the value $k_n : (k \rightarrow k_n)$

$$(9.1.2) \text{ Let : } \quad U_{2n} = U_{2(n-k_n)} + 2k_n \quad \text{and} \quad V_{2n} = V_{2(n-k_n)}$$

Assign to n the value $n + 1, (n \rightarrow n + 1$ and return to **A)**

End :

Outputs for integers less than 10^4 :

Print ($2n = \dots ; 2n - 3 = \dots ; W_{2n} = \dots ; T_{2n} = \dots ; V_{2n} = \dots ; U_{2n} = \dots$).

Outputs for large integers :

Print ($2n - P = \dots ; 2n - 3 - P = \dots ; W_{2n} - P = \dots ; T_{2n} = \dots ; V_{2n} - P = \dots ; U_{2n} = \dots$).

9.2 Program written with Maxima software for $2n = 10^{500}$.

```
r: 0 ; n1: 10**500 ; for n: 5*10**499 + 10000 thru 5*10**499 + 10010 do
(k: 1, a: 2*n, c: a - 3, test: 0, b: prev_prime(a - 1),
```

```

if primep(a - b)
then print(a - n1, c - n1, b - n1, a - b, b - n1, a - b)
otherwise ( r:r+ 1 ,
while test = 0 do
( if ( primep(c) and primep(a - c) )
then ( test:1 , print(a-n1 , a-n1-3 , b-n1 , a-b , c-n1 , a-c , " ** " , r))
else ( test : 0 , c : c - 2*k ))) );

```

10 Appendix

Application of Algorithm 9 : Table of U_{2n} and V_{2n} terms of the Goldbach sequence (G_{2n}) computed from program 9.2 , ($2 \leq 2n \leq 10^{1000} + 4020$).

The ** sign in the table below indicates the results given by the algorithm 9 in case **B**) of return to the previous terms of the sequence (G_{2n}). **WATCH OUT!** , for large integers n ($2n > 10^9$ for example), to simplify the display of large numbers, the results are entered as follows :

$$2n - P, (2n - 3) - P, W_{2n} - P, T_{2n}, V_{2n} - P \text{ and } U_{2n}$$

with ,

$$P = M, R, G, S, \text{ or } T \text{ constants defined in (2.3).}$$

$2n$	$2n - 3$	W_{2n}	$T_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n}$	V_{2n}	U_{2n}
4	1	X	X	2	2
6	3	3	3	3	3
8	5	5	3	5	3
10	7	7	3	7	3
12	9	7	5	7	5
14	11	11	3	11	3
16	13	13	3	13	3
18	15	13	5	13	5
20	17	17	3	17	3
22	19	19	3	19	3
24	21	19	5	19	5
26	23	23	3	23	3
28	25	23	5	23	5
30	27	23	7	23	7
32	29	29	3	29	3
34	31	31	3	31	3
36	33	31	5	31	5

38	35	31	7	31	7
40	37	37	3	37	3
80	77	73	7	73	7
82	79	79	3	79	3
84	81	79	5	79	5
86	83	83	3	83	3
88	85	83	5	83	5
90	87	83	7	83	7
92	89	89	3	89	3
94	91	89	5	89	5
96	93	89	7	89	7
**98	95	89	9	79	19
100	97	97	3	97	3
120	117	113	7	113	7
**122	119	113	9	109	13
124	121	113	11	113	11
126	123	113	13	113	13
**128	125	113	15	109	19
130	127	127	3	127	3
132	129	127	5	127	5
134	131	131	3	131	3
136	133	131	5	131	5
138	135	131	7	131	7
140	137	137	3	137	3
**500	497	491	9	487	13
502	499	499	3	499	3
504	501	499	5	499	5
506	503	503	3	503	3
508	505	503	5	503	5
510	507	503	7	503	7
1000	997	997	3	997	3
1002	999	997	5	997	5
1004	1001	997	7	997	7
**1006	1003	997	9	983	23
1008	1005	997	11	997	11
1010	1007	997	13	997	13
1012	1009	1009	3	1009	3
1014	1011	1009	5	1009	5
1016	1013	1013	3	1013	3
1018	1015	1013	5	1013	5

10002	9999	9973	29	9973	29
10004	10001	9973	31	9973	31
**10006	10003	9973	33	9923	83
**10008	10005	9973	35	9967	41
10010	10007	10007	3	10007	3
10012	10009	10009	3	10009	3
10014	10011	10009	5	10009	5
10016	10013	10009	7	10009	7
**10018	10015	10009	9	10007	11
10020	10017	10009	11	10009	11
2n - M (2n - 3) - M W_{2n} - M T_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n} V_{2n} - M U_{2n}					
+1000	+997	+993	7	+993	7
**+1002	+999	+993	9	+931	71
+1004	+1001	+993	11	+993	11
+1006	+1003	+993	13	+993	13
**+1008	+1005	+993	15	+919	89
+1010	+1007	+993	17	+993	17
+1012	+1009	+993	19	+993	19
+1014	+1011	+1011	3	+1011	3
+1016	+1013	+1011	5	+1011	5
+1018	+1015	+1011	7	+1011	7
**+1020	+1017	+1011	9	+931	89
2n - R (2n - 3) - R W_{2n} - R T_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n} V_{2n} - R U_{2n}					
**+1000	+997	+979	21	+903	97
+1002	+999	+979	23	+979	23
**+1004	+1001	+979	25	+951	53
**+1006	+1003	+979	27	+903	103
+1008	+1005	+979	29	+979	29
+1010	+1007	+979	31	+979	31
**+1012	+1009	+979	33	+951	61
**+1014	+1011	+979	35	+781	233
+1016	+1013	+979	37	+979	37
**+1018	+1015	+979	39	+951	67
+1020	+1017	+1017	3	+1017	3
2n - G (2n - 3) - G W_{2n} - G T_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n} V_{2n} - G U_{2n}					
**+10000	+9997	+9631	369	+7443	2557
**+10002	+9999	+9631	371	+9259	743
+10004	+10001	+9631	373	+9631	373
**+10006	+10003	+9631	375	+8583	1423
**+10008	+10005	+9631	377	+6637	3371

+10010	+10007	+9631	379	+9631	379
**+10012	+10009	+9631	381	+8583	1429
+10014	+10011	+9631	383	+9631	383
**+10016	+10013	+9631	385	+9259	757
**+10018	+10015	+9631	387	+4491	5527
+10020	+10017	+9631	389	+9631	389
$2n-S$	$(2n-3)-S$	$W_{2n}-S$	$T_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n}$	$V_{2n}-S$	U_{2n}
**+20000	+19997	+18031	1969	+17409	2591
**+20002	+19999	+18031	1971	+17409	2593
+20004	+20001	+18031	1973	+18031	1973
**+20006	+20003	+18031	1975	+16663	3343
**+20008	+20005	+18031	1977	+16941	3067
+20010	+20007	+18031	1979	+18031	1979
**+20012	+20009	+18031	1981	+5671	14341
**+20014	+20011	+18031	1983	+4101	15913
**+20016	+20013	+18031	1985	+3229	16787
+20018	+20015	+18031	1987	+18031	1987
**+20020	+20017	+18031	1989	+16941	3079
$2n-T$	$(2n-3)-T$	$W_{2n}-T$	$T_{2n} = 2n - W_{2n}$	$V_{2n} - T$	U_{2n}
**+40000	+39997	+29737	10263	+21567	18433
**+40002	+39999	+29737	10265	+22273	17729
+40004	+40001	+29737	10267	+29737	10267
**+40006	+40003	+29737	10269	+21567	18439
+40008	+40005	+29737	10271	+29737	10271
+40010	+40007	+29737	10273	+29737	10273
**+40012	+40009	+29737	10275	+10401	29611
**+40014	+40011	+29737	10277	-56003	96017
**+40016	+40013	+29737	10279	+27057	12959
**+40018	+40015	+29737	10281	+25947	14071
**+40020	+40017	+29737	10283	+24493	15527

11 Perspectives and generalizations

11.1 Other Goldbach sequences (G'_{2n}) and (G''_{2n}) independent of (G_{2n}) may be studied using the increasing sequences of primes (W'_{2n}), (see 8.5) and (W''_{2n}) defined by :

For any integer $n \geq 3$, $W''_{2n} = \text{Sup}(p \in \mathcal{P} : p \leq f(n))$, f being a function defined on the interval

$I = [3 ; +\infty[$ and satisfying the following conditions:

* f is strictly increasing on the interval I .

* $\lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} f(x) = +\infty ; f(3) = 3$.

* $\forall x \in I, f(x) \leq 2x - 3$.

For example, one of the following functions defined on I can be selected.

- a) $f : x \rightarrow ax + 3 - 3a ; \quad (a \in \mathbb{R} : 0 < a \leq 2)$.
- b) $g : x \rightarrow [4\sqrt{3x} - 9] \quad ([x]$ being the integer part of the real number x).
- c) $h : x \rightarrow 6\ln\left(\frac{x}{3}\right) + 3$.

11.2 Using this method, it would be interesting to study the Schnirelmann density [28] of certain primes such as 3, 5, 7, 11, in the sequence (U_{2n}) for $n \in [K_N ; P_N]$ as a function of N .

11.3 It is possible to exceed the values shown in the table ($2n = 10^{1000}$) by optimizing this algorithm, using supercomputers and more efficient software as Maple.

11.4 Diophantine equations and conjectures of the same nature (Lagrange-Lemoine-Levy conjecture [9], [17], [19],[21],[22], [30]) can be processed using similar reasoning and algorithms.

1) To validate the Lagrange_Lemoine-Levy conjecture, we can study the following sequences of primes (WL_{2n}) , (VL_{2n}) and (UL_{2n}) defined by :

For any integer $n \geq 3$, $WL_{2n} = \text{Sup}(p \in \mathcal{P} : p \leq n - 1)$,

a) If $TL_{2n} = (2n + 1 - 2WL_{2n})$ is a **prime**, then let : $VL_{2n} = WL_{2n}$ and $UL_{2n} = TL_{2n}$.

b) If TL_{2n} is a **composite number**, then there exists an integer k , ($1 \leq k \leq n - 3$) such that :

$UL_{2(n-k)} + 2k$ is a **prime** ; then let : $VL_{2n} = VL_{2(n-k)}$ and $UL_{2n} = UL_{2(n-k)} + 2k$.

2) Using the same type of reasoning, a generalized Bezout-Goldbach conjecture of the following form can be validated :

a) Let K and Q be two odd integers, prime to each other : for any integer n such that : $2n \geq 3(K + Q)$, there exist two primes U'''_{2n} and V'''_{2n} verifying :

$$KU'''_{2n} + QV'''_{2n} = 2n.$$

b) Let K and Q be two integers of different parity, prime to each other : for any integer n such that : $2n \geq 3(K + Q)$, there are two primes U'''_{2n} and V'''_{2n} verifying:

$$KU'''_{2n} + QV'''_{2n} = 2n + 1.$$

12 Conclusion

12.1 An unique recursive and explicit Goldbach sequence $(G_{2n}) = (U_{2n} ; V_{2n})$, verifying :

$$(\forall n \in \mathbb{N} + 2 \quad U_{2n} \text{ and } V_{2n} \text{ are primes} : U_{2n} + V_{2n} = 2n),$$

has been developed using an simple and efficient "local" algorithm.

12.2 Silva's [29] record is broken on a personal computer, and it is possible to reach values of the order of $2n = 10^{1000}$ with a reasonable computation time (less than three hours for the evaluation of ten terms U_{2n} and V_{2n}).

12.3 For a given integer $n \geq 49$, the evaluation of the terms U_{2n} and V_{2n} does not require the computing of all previous terms U_{2k} and V_{2k} , $(1 \leq k < n - 1)$. we just need to know the primes p_l, V_{2r} such that :

$$(12.3.1) \quad p_l \leq 7(\ln(2n))^{1.3} \quad \text{and} \quad 2n - 7(\ln(2n))^{1.3} \leq V_{2r} \leq 2n \quad \text{(on average).}$$

This property allows quick computing of U_{2n} and V_{2n} even for values of $2n$ of the order of 10^{1000} .

12.4 Therefore, the binary Goldbach and the Lagrange-Lemoine-Levy conjectures are true.

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